

Research Article

Development and Evaluation of a Thermosensitive in Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel of Moxifloxacin for Enhanced Ocular Retention and Sustained Drug Delivery

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The present study aimed to develop and evaluate a thermosensitive ocular in situ gel formulation of moxifloxacin for the treatment of bacterial eye infections with improved ocular residence time and sustained drug release. The formulations were prepared using Poloxamer 407 as a thermosensitive polymer, along with HPMC K4M and Carbopol 940 as viscosity-enhancing agents. The prepared formulations were evaluated for physicochemical parameters including appearance, pH, gelation temperature, viscosity, drug content, in-vitro drug release, ex-vivo corneal permeation, rheological properties, and stability studies. All formulations were found to be clear, with pH values within the acceptable ophthalmic range (6.5–7.4) and suitable gelation temperature close to physiological ocular temperature. The in-vitro drug release study demonstrated sustained drug release for up to 8 hours, with formulation F4 showing the highest cumulative drug release (94.5%). Ex-vivo permeation studies using goat cornea confirmed effective drug permeation across the corneal membrane, with formulation F1 exhibiting the highest permeation (82.12%) after 8 hours. Rheological evaluation indicated pseudoplastic (shear-thinning) behavior, which is desirable for ophthalmic drug delivery as it allows easy instillation while maintaining sufficient viscosity for prolonged ocular retention. Formulations containing Carbopol exhibited higher viscosity compared with HPMC-containing formulations due to stronger polymeric network formation. Stability studies conducted at refrigerated, room temperature, and accelerated conditions revealed that formulations F2 and F4 remained stable under refrigerated conditions, while slight instability was observed at higher temperatures during prolonged storage. Overall, the results demonstrate that thermosensitive in situ gel formulations of moxifloxacin can provide sustained drug release, improved corneal permeation, and prolonged ocular residence time, making them a promising approach for effective ocular drug delivery.

Keywords: Thermosensitive in situ gel, Moxifloxacin, Ocular drug delivery, Poloxamer 407, HPMC K4M, Carbopol 940, In-vitro drug release, Ex-vivo corneal permeation, Rheological studies, Stability studies.

INTRODUCTION

The eye is one of the most delicate and functionally complex organs of the human body, playing a critical role in visual perception and overall quality of life. Because of its constant exposure to the external environment, the eye is highly susceptible to a wide range of infections and inflammatory disorders that may impair vision if not treated effectively. Ocular diseases such as bacterial conjunctivitis, keratitis, and

other microbial infections require prompt therapeutic intervention to prevent complications and preserve visual function. For this purpose, ophthalmic drug delivery systems have been extensively developed to deliver therapeutic agents directly to ocular tissues. Among the available routes, topical administration in the form of eye drops remains the most widely used and patient-preferred method due to its simplicity, non-invasive nature, and ease of self-administration.¹⁻
² Despite its widespread use, topical ocular drug

delivery faces several physiological and anatomical barriers that limit drug absorption and therapeutic efficacy. The eye possesses efficient protective mechanisms such as blinking, tear production, and nasolacrimal drainage that rapidly eliminate instilled medications from the ocular surface. Additionally, the corneal epithelium acts as a strong barrier to drug permeation, further reducing drug penetration into deeper ocular tissues. As a result, only a small fraction of the administered drug is able to reach the target site, and the bioavailability of conventional ophthalmic formulations is often reported to be less than 10%. Due to this rapid elimination and poor drug retention, conventional eye drops must be administered frequently to maintain therapeutic drug levels, which can lead to poor patient compliance and inconsistent treatment outcomes.³⁻⁴ Traditional ophthalmic dosage forms such as solutions, suspensions, ointments, and inserts have been widely used for the treatment of ocular diseases. However, these conventional formulations present several drawbacks, including short precorneal residence time, rapid drug loss due to tear dilution, and variable drug absorption. In some cases, ointments may cause blurred vision and patient discomfort, while suspensions may show poor dose uniformity. Although the incorporation of viscosity-enhancing agents or mucoadhesive polymers has improved ocular retention to some extent, these approaches still fail to adequately overcome the rapid precorneal elimination of drugs. Therefore, the development of advanced drug delivery systems that can prolong ocular residence time and provide sustained drug release has become an important focus in ophthalmic pharmaceutical research. In recent years, in situ gelling drug delivery systems have emerged as a promising strategy for improving ocular drug bioavailability. These systems are designed as low-viscosity liquid formulations that undergo a sol-to-gel transition when exposed to physiological conditions such as temperature, pH, or ionic strength present in the ocular environment. Upon instillation into the eye, the formulation rapidly converts into a gel, forming a viscoelastic matrix that prolongs the residence time of the drug on the ocular surface. This transition helps reduce drug drainage, enhances drug absorption, and enables sustained release of the therapeutic agent over an extended period. Consequently, in situ gelling systems can significantly reduce dosing frequency and improve

patient adherence to therapy.⁵⁻⁸ Among the different types of stimuli-responsive systems, thermosensitive in situ hydrogels have gained considerable attention due to their practical advantages and patient convenience. These formulations remain in a liquid state at room temperature, allowing easy instillation into the eye, but undergo gelation at physiological temperature upon contact with the ocular surface. Thermosensitive polymers such as poloxamers are commonly used in these systems because they exhibit reversible phase transition properties and possess good biocompatibility. The resulting hydrogel forms a three-dimensional network structure that can encapsulate the drug and release it gradually, thereby maintaining therapeutic drug concentrations for a prolonged duration. Such systems offer a promising approach for enhancing ocular drug retention, improving bioavailability, and minimizing systemic absorption. Bacterial infections of the eye are among the most common ocular disorders and can lead to serious complications if not treated appropriately. Moxifloxacin, a fourth-generation fluoroquinolone antibiotic, is widely used in ophthalmology due to its broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens. It acts by inhibiting bacterial DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, thereby preventing bacterial replication and growth. Moxifloxacin is frequently prescribed for the treatment of bacterial conjunctivitis, keratitis, and other ocular infections. However, when administered in conventional eye drop formulations, the drug is rapidly washed away from the ocular surface, resulting in reduced therapeutic efficiency and the need for frequent dosing.⁷⁻¹⁰ To overcome these limitations, the development of an advanced ophthalmic formulation capable of enhancing drug retention and providing sustained release is highly desirable. Thermosensitive in situ hydrogels represent a promising platform for delivering antibiotics such as moxifloxacin more effectively. By undergoing gelation at ocular temperature, these systems can prolong drug contact time with the corneal surface, reduce drug loss through tear drainage, and maintain therapeutic concentrations for extended periods. Such formulations may significantly enhance ocular bioavailability while improving patient compliance and treatment efficacy.

Figure 1: Structure of Moxifloxacin

Therefore, the present study focuses on the development and evaluation of a thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogel of moxifloxacin aimed at improving ocular retention and achieving sustained drug delivery. The formulated system is designed to remain in liquid form during administration and undergo gelation upon exposure to physiological temperature in the eye. The developed hydrogel formulation is further evaluated for its physicochemical properties, gelation behavior, drug release characteristics, and overall suitability as an effective ophthalmic drug delivery system. Through this approach, the study seeks to provide an improved therapeutic strategy for the management of bacterial ocular infections while enhancing patient comfort and treatment outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

All chemicals and reagents used in the present investigation were of analytical grade and utilized as received without further purification. Moxifloxacin hydrochloride, the active pharmaceutical ingredient, was procured from a Ajantha pharmaceutical. Poloxamer 407, employed as the primary thermosensitive polymer for the preparation of the in-situ gelling system, was obtained from BASF Ltd., Mumbai, India. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) was used as a viscosity-enhancing and mucoadhesive polymer to improve the stability and ocular residence time of the formulation. Other excipients used in the formulation included benzalkonium chloride as a preservative, sodium chloride for isotonicity adjustment, and sodium hydroxide for pH adjustment of the formulation. Reagents such as sodium bicarbonate, calcium chloride dihydrate, disodium hydrogen phosphate,

and potassium dihydrogen phosphate were used in the preparation of simulated tear fluid for evaluation studies. All the excipients and analytical reagents were procured from M/s Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. Distilled water was used throughout the experimental work for the preparation of formulations and analytical studies. All materials used in the study complied with pharmaceutical grade standards and were considered suitable for the formulation and evaluation of the thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogel of moxifloxacin for enhanced ocular retention and sustained drug delivery.

METHODS:

Characterization of Moxifloxacin

The active pharmaceutical ingredient, moxifloxacin hydrochloride, was characterized using standard physicochemical and analytical techniques to confirm its identity and purity prior to formulation development. Initially, UV-visible spectrophotometric analysis was performed to determine the maximum absorbance wavelength (λ_{max}) of the drug. An accurately weighed quantity of moxifloxacin was dissolved in distilled water to prepare a solution of appropriate concentration, and the spectrum was scanned over a wavelength range of 200–400 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer to identify the characteristic absorption peak.¹¹ Further characterization of the drug and its compatibility with formulation excipients was carried out using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. A small quantity of the pure drug and a physical mixture of the drug with selected polymers were analyzed using an FTIR spectrophotometer to record the infrared spectra and identify the characteristic functional groups. The obtained spectra were evaluated to detect any possible

interactions between the drug and polymers used in the formulation. In addition, the melting point of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was determined using the capillary method to confirm the purity and identity of the drug. The observed melting point was compared with the reported literature values to ensure the authenticity of the drug used for the formulation study.

Construction of Calibration Curve of Moxifloxacin

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.4)

Phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 was prepared using potassium dihydrogen phosphate and sodium hydroxide. Initially, 27.22 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4) was dissolved in distilled water and the volume was adjusted to 1000 ml to obtain a stock solution. Subsequently, 50 ml of this solution was transferred into a 200 ml volumetric flask, followed by the addition of 39 ml of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide solution. The final volume was adjusted with distilled water to obtain phosphate buffer with a pH of 7.4.¹²

Calibration Curve in Phosphate Buffer

An accurately weighed 10 mg of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) to obtain a stock solution of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. From this stock solution, aliquots of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, and 1.4 ml were withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml with phosphate buffer to obtain solutions with concentrations ranging from 2–14 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The absorbance of each solution was measured using a UV–visible spectrophotometer at the λ_{max} of moxifloxacin (approximately 293 nm). A calibration curve was constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentration.¹³

Preparation of Simulated Tear Fluid (STF)

Simulated tear fluid was prepared to mimic the physiological conditions of the ocular environment. 0.670 g of sodium chloride, 0.200 g of sodium bicarbonate, and 0.008 g of calcium chloride dihydrate were dissolved in 100 ml of purified water with continuous stirring until a clear solution was obtained.¹⁴

Calibration Curve of Moxifloxacin in Simulated Tear Fluid

For the calibration curve in simulated tear fluid, 10 mg of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was accurately weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of STF to obtain a stock solution of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Aliquots of 0.2–1.4 ml were withdrawn and diluted up to 10 ml with STF to obtain concentrations ranging from 2–14 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The absorbance of the prepared solutions was measured using a UV–visible spectrophotometer at the λ_{max} of moxifloxacin, and a standard calibration curve was constructed.

Formulation Development of Thermosensitive In Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel of Moxifloxacin¹⁵⁻¹⁸

Method of Preparation

Thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogels of moxifloxacin were prepared using the cold method. Different formulations were developed by varying the concentration of Poloxamer 407 (Pluronic F127) as the primary thermosensitive gelling polymer in combination with secondary viscosity-enhancing polymers such as Carbopol 940 or Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC). Initially, aqueous dispersions of the selected concentrations of Carbopol 940 and HPMC were prepared separately in phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Subsequently, the required amount of Poloxamer 407 was gradually added to the polymer solutions with continuous stirring. The resulting dispersions were refrigerated for approximately 24 hours to allow complete dissolution of the polymer and obtain a clear homogeneous solution. Separately, the required quantity of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was dissolved in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Benzalkonium chloride (0.01%) was then added as a preservative with continuous stirring until a uniform drug solution was obtained. The prepared drug solution was slowly incorporated into the polymeric dispersion with continuous stirring to ensure uniform distribution of the drug within the formulation. The prepared in situ gel formulations were transferred into amber-colored glass containers to protect them from light. The filled containers were then subjected to thermal sterilization by autoclaving at 121°C under 15 psi pressure for 20 minutes. After sterilization, the formulations were stored under refrigerated conditions until further

evaluation and characterization studies were carried out.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

Table 1: Composition of Thermosensitive in Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel Formulations of Moxifloxacin

No.	Formulation Code	Moxifloxacin HCl (% w/v)	Poloxamer 407 (% w/v)	Carbopol 940 (% w/v)	HPMC K4M (% w/v)	Benzalkonium Chloride (% w/v)	Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.4)
1	F1	0.5	12	–	–	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
2	F2	0.5	12	0.02	–	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
3	F3	0.5	12	0.04	–	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
4	F4	0.5	12	–	0.5	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
5	F5	0.5	12	–	1.0	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
6	F6	0.5	18	–	–	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
7	F7	0.5	18	0.02	–	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
8	F8	0.5	18	0.04	–	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
9	F9	0.5	18	–	0.5	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml
10	F10	0.5	18	–	1.0	0.01	Q.S. to 100 ml

Ten different thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogel formulations of moxifloxacin hydrochloride were developed using Poloxamer 407 as the primary thermoreversible gelling polymer. Carbopol 940 and HPMC K4M were incorporated as secondary viscosity-enhancing and mucoadhesive polymers in varying concentrations to optimize gelation characteristics and ocular retention. Benzalkonium chloride (0.01% w/v) was used as a preservative, and phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) was used as the vehicle to maintain physiological compatibility.¹⁹

Evaluation of Formulations²⁰⁻⁴⁰

Determination of Visual Appearance and Clarity

Clarity is an important quality attribute of ophthalmic formulations because the presence of particulate matter may cause irritation or discomfort to the eye. Therefore, the prepared moxifloxacin in situ ophthalmic hydrogel formulations were visually inspected to ensure their suitability for ocular administration. Each formulation was examined

against both white and black backgrounds under adequate lighting conditions to detect the presence of any visible particles, turbidity, or cloudiness. Formulations that appeared clear and free from particulate matter were considered acceptable for further evaluation.

pH Determination

The pH of ophthalmic formulations plays a significant role in maintaining drug stability and ocular compatibility. A formulation with an inappropriate pH may cause irritation, lacrimation, and discomfort upon instillation. Ideally, ophthalmic formulations should possess a pH close to that of tear fluid, typically ranging between 5.0 and 7.4. The pH of the developed thermosensitive in situ hydrogel formulations of moxifloxacin was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter at room temperature. The measurements were performed to ensure that the formulations were within the acceptable physiological range and suitable for ocular administration.

Determination of Gelation Temperature

The gelation temperature represents the temperature at which the thermosensitive liquid formulation transforms into a gel, which is a critical parameter for in situ gelling systems. To determine the gelation temperature, 10 ml of the formulation was transferred into a transparent vial containing a magnetic stir bar. The vial was placed in a temperature-controlled water bath, and the temperature was gradually increased at a rate of approximately 2°C per minute while stirring continuously at 500 rpm. The temperature at which the magnetic bar ceased to move due to gel formation was recorded as the gelation temperature. The experiment was conducted in triplicate to ensure accuracy and reproducibility.

Effect of Dilution on Phase Transition Temperature

In vivo, ophthalmic formulations become diluted upon contact with tear fluid. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the effect of dilution on the phase transition behavior of the thermosensitive gel. For this study, the formulation was diluted with simulated tear fluid (STF) in a 40:7 ratio to mimic physiological conditions. The diluted sample was placed in a transparent beaker containing a magnetic stir bar and heated gradually while stirring at 100 rpm. The temperature at which gelation occurred, indicated by the cessation of magnetic stirring, was recorded as the phase transition temperature after dilution. This test helps predict the behavior of the formulation upon instillation into the eye.

Drug Content Determination

Drug content analysis was performed to ensure the uniform distribution and accurate concentration of moxifloxacin within the in situ gel formulations. An accurately weighed quantity of the formulation equivalent to 4 mg of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was dissolved in simulated tear fluid (pH 7.4) and stirred using a magnetic stirrer until complete dissolution was achieved. The solution was then filtered to remove any undissolved particles. From the filtrate, 10 ml of the solution was further diluted to 100 ml using simulated tear fluid. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer at the λ_{max} of moxifloxacin

(approximately 293 nm) against STF as a blank. The drug content was calculated using the standard calibration curve.

In-vitro Permeation Study

Franz Diffusion Cell Assembly

The in vitro drug permeation of moxifloxacin from the thermosensitive hydrogel formulations was evaluated using a Franz diffusion cell apparatus. A cellophane membrane was mounted between the donor and receptor compartments. The receptor compartment was filled with 20 ml of simulated tear fluid (STF) and maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to simulate physiological conditions. The hydrogel formulation containing 0.5% moxifloxacin was applied to the donor compartment. At predetermined time intervals, samples were withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with an equal volume of fresh STF to maintain sink conditions. The collected samples were analyzed using UV spectrophotometry to determine the amount of drug permeated.

Ex-vivo Corneal Permeation Study Using Goat Cornea

Ex-vivo permeation studies were performed using fresh goat corneas obtained from a local slaughterhouse. The excised corneas were carefully isolated and stored in cold simulated tear fluid until use. The cornea was mounted between the donor and receptor compartments of the Franz diffusion cell, with the epithelial side facing the donor compartment containing the formulation. The receptor compartment was filled with STF and maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with continuous stirring. Samples were collected at predetermined intervals and analyzed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer to determine the amount of drug permeated through the corneal membrane.

Rheological Study

The rheological behavior of the prepared formulations was evaluated to assess their viscosity and flow properties. The measurements were carried out using a Brookfield rheometer equipped with an appropriate spindle. The viscosity of the formulations was measured at different shear rates to determine their

flow characteristics. The analysis was conducted at 37°C, simulating physiological ocular temperature. Evaluation of rheological properties helps ensure that the formulation possesses appropriate viscosity for easy instillation in liquid form and sufficient gel strength after administration.

Stability Studies

The stability of the developed thermosensitive in situ hydrogel formulations was assessed according to standard stability testing conditions. The formulations were stored in sealed glass vials at different temperature conditions including refrigerated temperature (4°C), room temperature (25°C), and accelerated conditions (40°C) for a period of two months. Samples were withdrawn at 15-day intervals and evaluated for changes in appearance, pH, gelation temperature, drug content, and in vitro drug release profile. These studies were performed to ensure the physical and chemical stability of the formulation during storage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Pre-formulation Studies: Characterization of Moxifloxacin

The pre-formulation studies were performed to confirm the identity and purity of the drug prior to formulation development. Moxifloxacin hydrochloride was observed as a pale-yellow crystalline powder, which is consistent with the reported physical characteristics of the drug. The melting point was determined by the capillary method and found to be in the range of 235–238°C, which corresponds well with the literature values, confirming the purity and authenticity of the drug used in the study.

Spectroscopic Studies

UV Spectroscopy (Determination of λ_{max})

The UV absorption spectrum of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was recorded in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and simulated tear fluid (STF) over the wavelength range of 200–400 nm using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer.

The maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) of moxifloxacin was observed at 293 nm in both phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) and simulated tear fluid. This wavelength was selected for further quantitative analysis and calibration curve preparation.

Figure 2: U.V. spectra of moxifloxacin in PB F7.4

λ_{max} of moxifloxacin was found to be 293 nm in simulated tear fluid -STF

Figure 3: U.V. spectra of moxifloxacin in STF

Preparation of Calibration Curve of Moxifloxacin in Phosphate Buffer pH 7.4

A linear relationship was observed between concentration and absorbance in the range of 2–14

$\mu\text{g/ml}$, indicating adherence to Beer–Lambert’s law. The high correlation coefficient confirms excellent linearity of the analytical method.

Table 2: Calibration Curve of Moxifloxacin in Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.4)

Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	0	0.000
2	2	0.061
3	4	0.124
4	6	0.188
5	8	0.251
6	10	0.315
7	12	0.377
8	14	0.442

Figure 4: Calibration curve in PB pH 7.4

Preparation of Calibration Curve of Moxifloxacin in Simulated Tear Fluid

A linear calibration curve was also obtained in simulated tear fluid, demonstrating the suitability of

the method for drug estimation during *in-vitro* and *ex-vivo* studies. The strong correlation coefficient indicates good linearity and reliability of the spectrophotometric method.

Table 3: Calibration Curve of Moxifloxacin in STF

Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1	0	0.000
2	2	0.070
3	4	0.139
4	6	0.209
5	8	0.276
6	10	0.346
7	12	0.414
8	14	0.483

Figure 5: Calibration curve in STF

IR SPECTRUM INTERPRETATION:

The infrared spectrum of pure moxifloxacin was recorded and spectral analysis was done. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to evaluate the compatibility between moxifloxacin hydrochloride and the selected formulation excipients. The FTIR spectrum of the pure drug was recorded and compared with the spectra of physical mixtures containing the drug and polymers used in the formulation. The spectra were analyzed to identify the characteristic functional groups and to determine whether any chemical interaction occurred between the drug and excipients during formulation development. The FTIR spectrum of pure moxifloxacin hydrochloride exhibited characteristic absorption peaks corresponding to its functional groups, confirming the identity of the drug.

The spectra of the drug-polymer physical mixtures containing Poloxamer 407 with Carbopol 940 and Poloxamer 407 with HPMC K4M were also recorded and compared with that of the pure drug. The characteristic peaks of moxifloxacin were found to be retained in the spectra of the formulation blends without any significant shift or disappearance. The absence of major changes in the position or intensity of the characteristic peaks indicates that no significant chemical interaction occurred between moxifloxacin hydrochloride and the selected polymers or excipients. These findings confirm the compatibility of the drug with Poloxamer 407, Carbopol 940, and HPMC K4M, suggesting that these polymers are suitable for the development of a thermosensitive *in situ* ophthalmic hydrogel formulation of moxifloxacin.

Table 4: FTIR Spectral Interpretation of Moxifloxacin Hydrochloride

Sr. No.	Functional Group	Characteristic Peak of Pure Drug (cm ⁻¹)	Peak Observed in Drug–Polymer Mixture (cm ⁻¹)	Interpretation
1	O–H stretching	3420–3450	3422	Presence of hydroxyl group
2	N–H stretching	3300–3320	3305	Secondary amine stretching
3	C=O stretching (carbonyl)	1715–1730	1720	Carboxylic acid carbonyl vibration
4	C=O stretching (ketone)	1620–1650	1632	Ketone carbonyl group
5	C–F stretching	1240–1270	1256	Fluoroquinolone structure
6	C–N stretching	1090–1130	1112	Aromatic amine vibration
7	Aromatic C=C stretching	1500–1580	1545	Aromatic ring vibration

The FTIR spectra of moxifloxacin hydrochloride and its physical mixtures with Poloxamer 407, Carbopol 940, and HPMC K4M demonstrated that the characteristic peaks of the drug were preserved in the formulation blends. No significant shift in peak positions or disappearance of functional group peaks was observed. These results confirm that

moxifloxacin hydrochloride is chemically compatible with the selected polymers, indicating that the drug remains stable within the polymeric matrix. Therefore, Poloxamer 407 in combination with Carbopol 940 or HPMC K4M can be effectively used for the formulation of thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogels for sustained drug delivery.

Figure 6: FTIR spectrum of moxifloxacin hydrochloride

Figure 7: FTIR spectrum of drug + Poloxamer 407 + Carbopol 940

Figure 8: FTIR spectrum of drug + Poloxamer 407 + HPMC K4M

Formulation Study

Determination of Visual Appearance and Clarity

Visual appearance and clarity are important quality attributes for ophthalmic formulations because the presence of turbidity or particulate matter may cause discomfort or irritation upon ocular administration. Therefore, the prepared thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogel formulations of moxifloxacin hydrochloride (F1–F10) were visually inspected under adequate lighting conditions against white and black backgrounds to evaluate their clarity and transparency in both liquid and gel states.

The observations indicated that formulations F1–F5 appeared clear and transparent, whereas formulations F6–F10 exhibited slight turbidity and appeared cloudy. The difference in clarity is mainly attributed to the higher concentration of Poloxamer 407 (18%) used in formulations F6–F10. Increased concentration of poloxamer can lead to micelle aggregation within the polymeric solution, which may reduce transparency and result in a cloudy appearance. In contrast, formulations containing lower concentrations of Poloxamer 407 (12%) combined with HPMC K4M or Carbopol 940 showed better clarity and were considered more suitable for ophthalmic use.

Table 5: Visual Appearance of Moxifloxacin In Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel Formulations

Sr. No.	Formulation	Appearance of Solution	Appearance of Gel
1	F1	Transparent	Transparent
2	F2	Transparent	Transparent
3	F3	Transparent	Transparent
4	F4	Transparent	Transparent
5	F5	Transparent	Transparent
6	F6	Cloudy	Cloudy
7	F7	Cloudy	Cloudy
8	F8	Cloudy	Cloudy
9	F9	Cloudy	Cloudy
10	F10	Cloudy	Cloudy

Determination of pH of Formulations

The pH of ophthalmic preparations is a critical parameter because it directly influences drug stability, ocular comfort, and patient acceptability. Ideally, the pH of ophthalmic formulations should be close to the physiological pH of tear fluid, which is approximately 7.4, in order to minimize irritation upon administration. The pH values of the developed moxifloxacin in situ hydrogel formulations were

measured using a calibrated digital pH meter. The pH values were found to range between 6.8 and 7.4, which falls within the acceptable physiological range for ocular preparations. Among the tested formulations, F1, F2, and F4 exhibited pH values closest to the physiological tear pH, indicating better ocular compatibility. Therefore, these formulations are expected to cause minimal irritation when administered into the eye.

Table 6: pH of Moxifloxacin In Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel Formulations

Sr. No.	Formulation	pH
1	F1	7.3 ± 0.2
2	F2	7.2 ± 0.2
3	F3	7.1 ± 0.2
4	F4	7.4 ± 0.2
5	F5	7.1 ± 0.2
6	F6	7.0 ± 0.2
7	F7	6.9 ± 0.2
8	F8	6.8 ± 0.2
9	F9	7.0 ± 0.2
10	F10	6.8 ± 0.2

Determination of Gelation Temperature

Since the developed formulations are thermosensitive in situ gels, they should remain in liquid form at room temperature and undergo gelation when exposed to physiological ocular temperature. Therefore, determination of the gelation temperature is an essential parameter for evaluating thermoreversible formulations. The gelation temperature of the prepared formulations was determined using the magnetic stirring method. The results indicated that formulations F1–F5 exhibited gelation temperatures

close to physiological body temperature (34–38°C), making them suitable for ocular application. In contrast, formulations F6–F10 showed comparatively lower gelation temperatures, which may be attributed to the higher concentration of Poloxamer 407 used in these formulations. It was observed that increasing the concentration of Poloxamer 407 resulted in a decrease in gelation temperature due to enhanced micelle formation and polymer network development. Similarly, increasing the concentration of HPMC K4M or Carbopol 940 slightly influenced the gelation behavior of the formulations.

Table 7: Gelation Temperature of Moxifloxacin In Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel Formulations

Sr. No.	Formulation	Gelation Temperature (°C)
1	F1	38 ± 1
2	F2	36 ± 1
3	F3	34 ± 1
4	F4	36 ± 1
5	F5	35 ± 1
6	F6	32 ± 1
7	F7	30 ± 1
8	F8	28 ± 1
9	F9	32 ± 1
10	F10	27 ± 1

Effect of Dilution on Phase Transition Temperature

Since the developed formulations are thermosensitive in situ gels, it is important to evaluate their gelation behavior after dilution with tear fluid. Upon instillation into the eye, the formulation mixes with the tear fluid, which may influence the gelation temperature. Therefore, the effect of dilution on phase transition temperature was investigated using simulated tear fluid. The results indicated that the gelation temperature increased by approximately 2–5°C after dilution compared to the gelation

temperature before dilution. This shift occurs due to the dilution of the polymer concentration when the formulation comes in contact with tear fluid, resulting in a slight delay in gel formation. Among the tested formulations, F2, F3, F4, and F5 exhibited gelation temperatures close to physiological ocular temperature after dilution, indicating their suitability for ocular administration. These formulations remained in liquid form at room temperature but rapidly converted into gel at ocular temperature, which is desirable for prolonged ocular residence time.

Table 8: Effect of Dilution on Gelation Temperature of Moxifloxacin In Situ Gel Formulations

Sr. No.	Formulation	Gelation Temperature (°C)	Gelation Temperature After Dilution (°C)
1	F1	38 ± 1	43 ± 1
2	F2	36 ± 1	38 ± 1
3	F3	34 ± 1	37 ± 1
4	F4	36 ± 1	38 ± 1
5	F5	35 ± 1	38 ± 1
6	F6	32 ± 1	35 ± 1
7	F7	30 ± 1	35 ± 1
8	F8	28 ± 1	33 ± 1
9	F9	32 ± 1	35 ± 1
10	F10	27 ± 1	30 ± 1

Drug Content Determination

Drug content analysis was performed to evaluate the uniform distribution of moxifloxacin hydrochloride within the polymeric matrix of the in situ gel formulations. The percentage drug content of all formulations was found within the acceptable range,

indicating uniform drug distribution and minimal drug loss during formulation preparation. The drug content values ranged from 96.38% to 99.65%, demonstrating good formulation reproducibility and homogeneity. These results confirm that the drug was properly incorporated into the polymeric system without significant degradation.

Table 9: Drug Content of Moxifloxacin in Situ Ophthalmic Hydrogel Formulations

Sr. No.	Formulation	Drug Content (%)
1	F1	96.38 ± 0.40
2	F2	98.63 ± 0.38
3	F3	99.21 ± 0.39
4	F4	98.45 ± 0.47
5	F5	99.65 ± 0.35
6	F6	99.36 ± 0.51
7	F7	98.96 ± 0.36
8	F8	97.51 ± 0.45
9	F9	99.47 ± 0.31
10	F10	99.45 ± 0.47

***In-vitro* Drug Release Study**

The in vitro permeation study of moxifloxacin from thermosensitive in situ hydrogel formulations was performed using a Franz diffusion cell system. The results demonstrated that the drug was released from the hydrogel matrix through a diffusion-controlled mechanism, providing sustained drug release over an extended period. Poloxamer 407 in combination with HPMC K4M or Carbopol 940 formed a three-dimensional gel network that controlled drug diffusion and increased ocular residence time. The

results revealed that increasing the concentration of viscosity-enhancing polymers (HPMC K4M or Carbopol 940) reduced the rate of drug release due to increased gel viscosity and stronger polymeric network formation. Formulation F4 exhibited the highest drug release (94.5%) after 8 hours, indicating an optimal balance between gel strength and drug diffusion. These findings suggest that lower concentrations of HPMC or Carbopol with an appropriate concentration of Poloxamer 407 provide optimal sustained drug release and improved ocular retention.

Table 10: *In-vitro* Drug Release Profile of Moxifloxacin In Situ Gel Formulations (F1–F5)

Time (hr)	F1 (%CDR)	F2 (%CDR)	F3 (%CDR)	F4 (%CDR)	F5 (%CDR)
0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	4.50 ±0.26	7.87 ±0.35	10.12 ±0.25	7.87 ±0.54	10.12 ±0.68
1	10.12 ±0.65	14.62 ±0.14	18.00 ±0.35	15.75 ±0.21	18.00 ±0.76
1.5	16.87 ±0.16	21.37 ±0.42	25.87 ±0.21	22.50 ±0.68	25.87 ±0.24
2	23.62 ±0.94	30.37 ±0.12	32.62 ±0.64	31.50 ±0.96	34.87 ±0.29
2.5	30.37 ±0.41	39.37 ±0.18	39.37 ±0.85	40.50 ±1.10	43.87 ±0.96
3	38.25 ±0.21	45.00 ±0.84	48.37 ±1.40	49.50 ±0.32	52.87 ±0.65
4	48.37 ±0.37	58.50 ±0.94	57.37 ±0.98	56.25 ±0.47	59.62 ±0.86
5	59.62 ±0.65	67.50 ±1.20	65.25 ±0.62	65.25 ±0.56	69.75 ±1.20
6	68.62 ±0.12	76.50 ±1.40	70.87 ±0.94	74.25 ±0.58	76.50 ±0.98
7	82.12 ±0.93	82.12 ±0.85	77.62 ±0.74	84.37 ±0.52	84.37 ±0.36
8	91.12 ±0.22	87.75 ±0.54	85.50 ±0.88	94.50 ±0.32	92.25 ±0.55

Figure 9: In-vitro drug release profile of moxifloxacin thermosensitive in situ ophthalmic hydrogel formulations (F1-F5)

Ex-vivo Corneal Permeation Study Using Goat Cornea

Ex-vivo corneal permeation studies of moxifloxacin thermosensitive in situ hydrogel formulations (F1-F5) were carried out using freshly excised goat cornea mounted on a Franz diffusion cell apparatus. Simulated tear fluid (STF, pH 7.4) was used as the receptor medium to mimic physiological ocular conditions. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined time intervals up to 8 hours, and the amount of drug permeated through the corneal membrane was determined spectrophotometrically. The obtained results indicated that all formulations showed a sustained permeation pattern through the corneal membrane over the experimental period. The cumulative percentage drug permeation after 8 hours was found to be 82.12%, 74.25%, 70.87%, 78.75%, and 76.00% for formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, and F5, respectively. Among the tested formulations, F1 exhibited the highest drug permeation, suggesting a comparatively lower viscosity and weaker gel network which facilitated faster drug diffusion

through the corneal membrane. Formulations containing HPMC (F4 and F5) demonstrated comparatively higher permeation than some formulations containing Carbopol, which may be attributed to differences in polymer swelling behavior and gel matrix structure. The presence of Poloxamer 407 combined with viscosity-enhancing polymers formed a gel network capable of controlling drug diffusion and prolonging the residence time of the formulation on the ocular surface. Although the ex-vivo conditions differ from the physiological environment of the human eye, the results indicate that the developed in situ gels are capable of retaining the drug and providing sustained release for an extended period (up to 8 hours). In the ocular cul-de-sac, the gel may undergo gradual dissolution due to blinking and eye movements; however, the limited volume of lachrymal fluid (approximately 7.5–10 μ L) suggests that the drug release in vivo may occur more slowly compared to in-vitro conditions. These findings confirm the potential of the developed thermosensitive in situ gel system for prolonged ocular drug delivery of moxifloxacin.

Table 11: Ex-vivo Corneal Permeation Profile of Moxifloxacin In Situ Gel Formulations (F1-F5)

Sr. No.	Time (hr)	F1 (% Drug Release \pm SD)	F2 (% Drug Release \pm SD)	F3 (% Drug Release \pm SD)	F4 (% Drug Release \pm SD)	F5 (% Drug Release \pm SD)
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.5	6.75 \pm 0.65	2.25 \pm 0.84	4.50 \pm 0.20	6.75 \pm 0.24	4.50 \pm 0.30
3	1	13.50 \pm 0.35	9.00 \pm 0.50	11.25 \pm 0.50	13.50 \pm 0.78	10.12 \pm 0.40

4	1.5	20.25 ±0.25	14.62 ±0.58	19.12 ±0.24	21.37 ±0.35	16.50 ±0.50
5	2	29.25 ±0.25	21.37 ±0.78	25.87 ±0.25	29.25 ±0.42	23.60 ±0.25
6	2.5	37.12 ±0.52	29.25 ±0.12	33.75 ±0.65	36.00 ±0.13	30.50 ±0.69
7	3	45.00 ±0.61	36.00 ±1.10	40.50 ±0.25	42.75 ±0.29	38.20 ±0.36
8	4	52.87 ±0.80	42.75 ±0.98	45.00 ±0.52	48.37 ±0.72	43.80 ±0.75
9	5	59.62 ±0.78	51.75 ±0.45	52.87 ±0.55	55.12 ±0.89	51.00 ±0.12
10	6	66.37 ±0.41	59.62 ±0.23	57.37 ±0.75	63.00 ±0.10	59.60 ±0.25
11	7	74.25 ±0.32	67.50 ±0.65	64.12 ±0.14	72.00 ±0.36	67.00 ±0.50
12	8	82.12 ±1.10	74.25 ±0.40	70.87 ±0.25	78.75 ±0.66	76.00 ±0.75

Figure 10: Ex-vivo drug release profile of Moxifloxacin in situ gel

Rheological Studies

Rheological evaluation is an important parameter for thermosensitive in situ gel systems as it significantly influences drug retention, ease of instillation, and overall in-vivo ocular performance. An ideal ophthalmic formulation should possess moderate viscosity to allow easy administration into the eye, while still maintaining sufficient viscosity after gelation to prevent rapid drainage from the ocular surface. Excessively high viscosity may lead to difficulty during instillation, whereas very low viscosity may result in rapid elimination of the formulation through lacrimal drainage. The dynamic viscosity of the poloxamer-based formulations was measured at different shear rates under simulated physiological conditions. The results indicated that the viscosity of all formulations decreased with increasing shear rate, demonstrating pseudoplastic (shear-thinning) behavior. This type of rheological behavior is desirable for ophthalmic drug delivery systems because it allows the formulation to remain

viscous at rest while becoming less viscous during blinking. During blinking, the shear rate in the eye can vary widely (approximately 0.03 s^{-1} to $28,500 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Therefore, formulations exhibiting pseudoplastic flow are advantageous as they provide high viscosity at low shear rates, which helps retain the formulation in the conjunctival sac, and lower viscosity at high shear rates, which facilitates comfortable blinking and spreading of the formulation across the ocular surface. The rheological study also revealed differences among the formulations based on polymer composition. Formulations containing Carbopol (F2 and F3) showed higher viscosity values compared with formulations containing HPMC (F4 and F5) due to stronger polymeric network formation. In contrast, formulation F1, which did not contain Carbopol or HPMC, exhibited comparatively lower viscosity. Overall, the viscosity values of all formulations were found to be within the acceptable range for ocular in situ gel systems, indicating suitable rheological characteristics for ophthalmic application.

Table 12: Rheological Study of Moxifloxacin In Situ Gel Formulations (F1–F5)

Sr. No.	Shear Rate (1/s)	F1 (Viscosity cp)	F2 (Viscosity cp)	F3 (Viscosity cp)	F4 (Viscosity cp)	F5 (Viscosity cp)
1	0.03	55246	62897	64265	56136	58614
2	0.1	49358	55691	56187	50127	51237
3	0.3	39963	46148	48893	40012	42658
4	0.9	33568	39682	41864	34038	35896
5	2.7	24887	28634	30452	27896	29468
6	8.1	14423	15469	16336	14934	15622
7	14.6	3238	9942	8421	4623	6026

Figure 11: Rheological profile of Moxifloxacin in-situ gel formulations

Stability Study

Stability studies were performed for optimized moxifloxacin in situ gel formulations (F2 and F4) under different storage conditions, including refrigerated temperature (4 °C), room temperature (25 °C), and elevated temperature (40 °C) for a period of 60 days. The formulations were evaluated at predetermined time intervals for appearance, pH, gelation temperature, drug content, and in-vitro drug release. At refrigerated temperature, both formulations (F2 and F4) remained transparent throughout the study period. The pH of the formulations remained close to the physiological ocular pH (~7.4), and no significant changes were observed in gelation temperature, drug content, or percentage drug release. This indicates that the formulations were physically and chemically stable under refrigerated conditions. At room temperature

(25 °C), the formulations maintained acceptable characteristics up to 45 days, showing transparent appearance, near-neutral pH, and minimal variation in gelation temperature, drug content, and drug release. However, by 60 days, slight instability was observed as the formulations became cloudy with a decrease in pH, indicating partial precipitation of the drug and reduced stability. Similarly, at elevated temperature (40 °C), both formulations showed acceptable stability up to 30 days. Beyond this period, the formulations exhibited changes in appearance (cloudiness) and slight pH variations, indicating decreased stability under accelerated conditions. From these observations, it can be concluded that the optimized in situ gel formulations F2 and F4 showed better stability under refrigerated storage conditions, while formulations stored at room temperature and elevated temperature exhibited comparatively lower stability over prolonged storage.

Table 13: Combined Stability Study of Optimized Formulations (F2 and F4)

Formulation	Storage Temp	Time (Days)	Appearance	pH	Gelation Temp (°C)	Drug Content (%)	In-vitro Release (%)
F2	4°C	15	Transparent	7.0	35	98.18	75.49
F2	4°C	30	Transparent	7.1	35	97.21	74.89
F2	4°C	45	Transparent	7.1	35.5	96.54	72.78
F2	4°C	60	Transparent	7.3	36	96.43	72.58
F4	4°C	15	Transparent	7.1	35	99.00	76.74
F4	4°C	30	Transparent	7.1	36	98.74	75.65
F4	4°C	45	Transparent	7.3	37	96.75	73.71
F4	4°C	60	Transparent	7.4	37	96.20	72.72
F2	25°C	15	Transparent	7.3	35	98.35	74.84
F2	25°C	30	Transparent	7.4	36	98.25	72.23
F2	25°C	45	Transparent	7.6	36.4	97.28	72.02
F2	25°C	60	Cloudy	6.2	36.5	96.78	71.45
F4	25°C	15	Transparent	7.4	33	98.63	77.54
F4	25°C	30	Transparent	7.5	34	98.21	76.49
F4	25°C	45	Transparent	7.0	35	97.75	75.78
F4	25°C	60	Cloudy	6.9	35.3	95.63	72.72
F2	40°C	15	Transparent	7.1	–	97.52	73.49
F2	40°C	30	Transparent	6.8	–	96.74	73.28
F2	40°C	45	Cloudy	6.3	–	95.41	73.56
F2	40°C	60	Cloudy	5.8	–	95.69	72.89
F4	40°C	15	Transparent	7.4	–	99.08	76.79
F4	40°C	30	Transparent	7.3	–	96.21	75.94
F4	40°C	45	Cloudy	7.3	–	94.94	73.45
F4	40°C	60	Cloudy	7.4	–	94.13	73.87

CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully developed thermosensitive in situ gel formulations of moxifloxacin intended for sustained ocular drug delivery. The formulations prepared using Poloxamer 407 in combination with HPMC K4M or Carbopol 940 demonstrated suitable physicochemical and rheological characteristics for ophthalmic administration. All formulations showed acceptable clarity, pH, gelation temperature, and drug content, indicating good compatibility between the drug and excipients. The in-vitro drug release study confirmed sustained drug release up to 8 hours, with formulation F4 providing the highest cumulative drug release. Ex-vivo permeation studies using goat cornea further demonstrated effective drug permeation through the corneal membrane. The rheological study revealed pseudoplastic flow behavior, which is advantageous for ocular drug delivery systems as it facilitates easy instillation and reduces drug loss through lacrimal

drainage while maintaining prolonged retention in the conjunctival sac. Stability studies indicated that formulations F2 and F4 remained stable under refrigerated conditions, while slight instability was observed at room and elevated temperatures after prolonged storage. Overall, the developed moxifloxacin thermosensitive in situ gel system shows potential as an effective ocular drug delivery system, providing sustained drug release, improved corneal permeation, and enhanced ocular residence time, which may improve therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance in the treatment of bacterial ocular infections.

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS:

All authors have declared no conflict of interest.

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